

Effective adsorption of anionic dye, Orange G, from aqueous solutions onto activated carbon derived from saw dust by chemical activation with perchloric acid

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Abstract : Present communication addressed the applicability of a low cost activated carbon derived from 'perchloric acid activated saw dust' as an alternate for the contemporary expensive methods for the removal of anionic textile dye from aqueous solutions. Dynamic batch mode operation was set up for the study of various factors such as pH, contact time and temperature, affecting the removal of dye. The surface characterization of the activated carbon was carried out by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR). The process of removal was found to be fast and equilibrium was established in 50 min. The maximum removal obtained was 95.67% at pH 2.0, temperature 30 °C, 50 mg L⁻¹ initial concentration and a 10 g/L of adsorbent dose. The kinetic study reveals that the data was in close agreement with pseudo-second order than pseudo-first order expression. Equilibrium isotherm was analyzed by fitting the data into Langmuir and Freundlich models. The data are better fitted by Freundlich isotherm as compared with Langmuir. The calculated adsorption capacity of activated carbon was 64.93 mg/g at 30 °C. The thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were calculated for the removal process. The negative values of ΔH° and ΔG° indicates the exothermic and spontaneous nature of the process, respectively. According to these results, the activated carbon synthesized could be used as an alternate to the expensive commercial activated carbon for the removal of textiles dyes from waste water.

Keywords : Activated carbon, kinetics, equilibrium isotherm, thermodynamics.

Introduction

The world demand of activated carbon is steadily increasing due to its well-known extensive use as adsorbent for purification and separation in many processes¹. The most commonly used adsorbent for the removal of dyes is mainly commercial coal-based activated carbon due to its high sorption capacity and extensive surface area. But, its use is limited because of its soaring price and high operation and regeneration costs. However, the demand for coal-based carbon has been growing interest in all of countries. This leads to the investigation of cheap and easily available material that can be used for the preparation of activated carbon. There have been many reports on the production of activated carbon to use as adsorbent for elimination of hazardous materials from wastewater. Many cheap plants based waste materials such as coconut coir dust, plum kernels, rice barn, apricot stone shells, parthenium biomass²⁻⁶ etc. have been utilized as source

of activated carbon by several researchers for removal of dye bearing effluents. There are two basic processes to activate carbon materials; physical activation and chemical activation. Chemical activation can be accomplished in a single step by means of thermal decomposition of raw materials with chemical reagents⁷. Chemical modification processes have been executed by several workers with acidic reagents H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄^{7,8}, with basic reagents NaOH, K₂CO₃^{9,10} etc.

The present investigation deals with the production of activated carbon by chemical activation of saw dust and to assess its sorption capacity on Orange G. Orange G (Fig. 1) is a toxic dye with many after effects on human beings and has applications in a large number of industries. An exposure to Orange G has been reported to cause vomiting, dizziness, cyanosis, increased blood pressure and jaundice in humans¹¹. This study utilizes perchloric acid as a chemical reagent intended for activation

Fig.1. Molecular structure of Orange G.

of saw dust for the first time, till now no data being available regarding perchloric acid activation. This work further contributes in comparison of adsorption capacities of various adsorbents activated with different chemical reagents. The equilibrium and kinetic data of the adsorption process of Orange G dye molecules onto prepared activated carbon were carried out in this study.

Results and discussion

Characterization of activated carbon :

The FTIR spectrum of raw sawdust (Fig. 2a) exhibited O-H stretching band on spectrum in the range of 3200–3400 cm^{-1} . A greater number of OH groups on the glucose units of the cellulose polymers broaden the peak. The peak at 1050–1610 cm^{-1} was assigned to the C=O bonds. The absorption bands at 2928.47 and 2880.23 cm^{-1} are due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the methylene group and their bending vibrations are between 1421 and 1371 cm^{-1} . These medium stretching bands show presence of vinyl and methyl groups. Major band between 500 and 600 denotes the C-Br group.

The FTIR spectrum of the activated carbon (Fig. 2b) shows a band at 3433 cm^{-1} ascribed to OH⁻ stretching

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra : (a) raw sawdust, (b) activated carbon of sawdust.

vibration and its peak intensity is much lower than that of FTIR spectrum of raw sawdust. This difference is due to the fact that HClO_4 leads to cleavage of bond, initiated dehydration as well as elimination reactions that liberate volatile materials such as water, acetic acid, methanol etc. Two weak bands at around $2950\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed and represented aliphatic groups stretching vibration, but their intensities were lower than that of spectrum of the raw sawdust as it may be due to increase of temperature that causes decrease in aliphaticity. It is also observed that there is decrease of a band at 1610 cm^{-1} that assigned to $\text{C}=\text{C}$ skeletal stretching in condensed aromatic system. So from the preceded outcome it can be concluded that carbonization of raw sawdust leads to enhancement of aromaticity as well as decomposition of a number of structures¹³.

Effect of pH :

Fig. 3 depicted the effect of different pH on removal process of Orange G. Solution pH plays an important role in controlling the surface charge of the adsorbent, the degree of ionization of adsorbate in the solution as well as dissociation of various functional groups on the active sites of the adsorbent¹². The adsorption experiment of anionic dye was performed at different pH range

of 2–10 at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 50 min. The equilibrium sorption capacity was lowest at pH 10 (4.46 mg/g) and maximum adsorption of dye was achieved at pH 2 (5.12 mg/g). This can be explained as in the aqueous solution the anionic dye exists in dissociated form as anionic dye ions. At lower pH significantly high electrostatic force of attraction exists between the positively charged surface of activated carbon and anionic dye hence enhance more dye uptake. With the increase of pH beyond 6 the numbers of negatively charged sites increased results in reduction of positively charged sites. This condition does not favor the uptake of anion from the system and leads to electrostatic repulsion.

Zero point charge of the adsorbent :

The zero point charge, pH_{zpc} , of raw saw dust was determined by titration method and was found to be 5.5. At a pH greater than the pH_{zpc} of the adsorbent, the surface of adsorbent is negatively charged and favored cationic adsorption from the solution; and when solution $\text{pH} < \text{pH}_{\text{zpc}}$, the surface of adsorbent is positively charged and attractive to anions¹³. In the present studies (Fig. 4), a low pH was favorable for adsorption of the anionic dye (Orange G) by activated carbon of sawdust. As pH of the system decreased, the number of negatively charged ad-

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on removal of Orange G dye (50 mg/L concentration) by adsorption on activated carbon.

Fig. 4. pH_{zpc} of activated carbon.

sorbent sites decreased and number of positively charged surface sites increased, which favors the adsorption of negatively charged dye anions due to electrostatic attraction. Also lower adsorption of Orange G at basic pH is due to the presence of excess of OH^- ions competing with dye for adsorption sites.

Effect of initial concentration of the dye on removal :

The adsorption capacity of the dyes was dependent on the concentration of the dyes. Initially, dye molecules have to first come across the boundary layer effect. Then it has to diffuse from boundary layer film onto adsorbent surface and finally, it has to diffuse into the porous structure of the adsorbent. The initial dye concentration provides an important driving force to overcome all mass transfer resistance of all molecules between the aqueous and solid phases. The effect of the initial concentration of Orange G in range of (50 to 200) mg/L was studied at the pH of 2 using adsorbent dose of 10 g/L. Increasing initial dye concentrations leads to an increase in the amount of adsorbed dye this suggests that the sites available on the adsorbent are the limiting factor for dye sorption. By increasing initial dye concentrations the percentage removal of dye decreased (Fig. 5) from 93.8% to 82.8%,

conversely the actual amount of dye uptake per unit mass decreased from 16.57 mg/L to 4.69 mg/L. The increase for amount of dye uptake with increase of initial concentration is due to the decrease in resistance to the uptake of solute from dye solution.

Effect of contact time and temperature :

The effect of contact time on the amount of Orange G, adsorbed onto activated carbon at various temperatures (Fig. 6) was also studied with 50 mg/L of dye solutions. The removal of dye onto adsorbent was fast initially then slows down gradually until equilibrium condition reached. Beyond attainment of equilibrium there was no significant increase in the removal. Maximum removal of dye onto activated carbon was observed at 50 min, thus selected as the equilibrium contact time.

The equilibrium adsorption capacity of Orange G onto activated carbon was also affected by temperature and removal capacity decreased with increase of temperature from 30 °C to 50 °C which indicates that removal process favors at low temperature and it is controlled by an exothermic process. This may be attributed to the either decrease in active sites over surface of adsorbent or the increase in the thickness of the boundary layer surrounding the adsorbent with temperature.

Fig. 5. Effect on initial concentration on the removal of Orange G by activated carbon at temperature of 30 °C and pH 2.

Adsorption kinetics for the removal of dye :

Pseudo-first order model :

The kinetic studies for the removal of Orange G were undertaken by fitting the kinetic data in linearized form of Lagergren's equation¹⁴ :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - (K_{ad}/2.303) t \quad (1)$$

where q_e and q (both in mg/g) are amounts of Orange G adsorbed at any time and at equilibrium, respectively, and K_{ad} (min^{-1}) is the rate constant of adsorption. Graphs of the figure ' $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t ' are straight line (Fig. 7). The values of first order rate constant were determined by slopes of the straight line plots are presented in Table 1. The values of the rate constant were found to be decreased from 0.133 min^{-1} to 0.108 min^{-1} with increase of temperature from 30 °C to 50 °C. This suggests that the process of dye removal is exothermic in nature.

Pseudo-second order model :

The pseudo-second order kinetic equation is based on the sorption capacity of the solid phase. The following linearized form of the pseudo-second order equation¹⁵ was used in the present studies :

$$t/qt = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \quad (2)$$

where, k_2 and q_e values were determined from the slope and intercepts of the linear plots of t/qt against t (Fig. 8), respectively and are presented in Table 1. The values of correlation coefficients (R^2) were closer to unity and the calculated values of q_e nearly equals to the experimental values of q_e which supports that the adsorption of the dye on activated carbon followed pseudo-second order kinetics better.

Adsorption isotherm :

Langmuir isotherm model :

The Langmuir adsorption isotherm model is based on the assumption that during the process of removal, the adsorbent surface is covered by a monolayer of the adsorbate species.

For the present studies, the linearized form of expression of Langmuir model was used¹⁶ :

$$C_e/q_e = C_e/q_m + 1/K_L q_m \quad (3)$$

where C_e (mg L^{-1}), q_e (mg g^{-1}) are the concentrations of adsorbate and amount of adsorbate adsorbed at equilibrium, respectively. The constant K_L (L/g) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and q_m gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity, Q^0 .

Fig. 6. Effect of contact time and temperature for the adsorption of dye Orange G (concentration 50 mg/L) onto activated carbon.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for the removal of Orange G by adsorption on activated carbon at different temperatures

Kinetic models and its parameters	Temperatures (°C)		
	30	40	50
q_e , exp (mg/g)	4.69	4.57	4.48
Pseudo-first order kinetic :			
$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	5.11	4.52	3.68
k_1 (min^{-1})	0.134	121	0.108
R^2	0.971	0.979	0.973
Pseudo-second-order kinetic :			
$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	4.81	4.56	4.39
k_2 (g/mg/min)	0.038	0.041	0.044
h (mg/g/min)	0.879	0.852	0.847
R^2	0.998	0.998	0.999

Table 2. The related parameters for the adsorption isotherm of Orange G on activated carbon at different temperatures

Adsorption isotherms and its constant	Temperatures (°C)		
	30	40	50
Langmuir adsorption isotherm constant :			
K_L (L/g)	0.022	0.018	0.016
Q^0 (mg/g)	64.93	58.13	53.47
R_L	0.476	0.526	0.555
R^2	0.974	0.977	0.982
Freundlich adsorption isotherm constants :			
K_f (mg/g) (L/mg) $^{1/n}$	8.37	4.17	2.64
$1/n$	3.29	3.99	4.44
R^2	0.991	0.998	0.991

The essential factor of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in term of a dimensionless constant called separation factor (R_L , also called equilibrium parameter) which is defined by the following equation :

$$R_L = 1/1 + K_L C_0 \quad (4)$$

where C_0 (mg/L) is the initial adsorbate concentration and q_m (mg/g) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption. The value of R_L indicates the shape of the isotherm to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$). Linear

($R_L = 1$). Favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$).

The equilibrium data was plotted for ' C_e/q_e vs C_e '. The values of Q^0 and K_L , the two constants were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the figure (Fig. not shown) and the values are given in Table 2. It is evident from the Table 2 that with the increase in temperature from 30 °C to 50 °C monolayer adsorption capacity (Q^0) values decreases from 64.97 mg/g to 53.47 mg/g. The decreasing values of Q^0 with increasing tem-

Fig. 7. Pseudo-first order kinetic plot for the removal of Orange G (concentration 50 mg/L) at different temperatures by activated carbon.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of Orange G dye over activated carbon

Temp. (T) (K)	Standard Gibbs free energy change ΔG° (kJ/mol)	Standard enthalpy change ΔH° (kJ/mol)	Standard entropy change ΔS° (J/mol K)
303	-16.20	-8.41	30.01
313	-17.41		
323	-17.77		

perature clearly suggest that the ongoing adsorption process is exothermic in nature.

Freundlich isotherm :

Adsorption data for the dye on raw saw dust was also fitted to the linear form of Freundlich isotherm¹⁷ :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \quad (5)$$

where K_f (mg g^{-1}) is the Freundlich constant and n is the Freundlich exponent. The equilibrium data was plotted for $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ enables the constant K_f and exponent n to be determined, q_e is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbate, C_e the equilibrium concentra-

tion, and $1/n$ and K_f are constants. The constant K_f is related to the degree of adsorption, n provides the tentative estimation of the intensity of the adsorption. The Freundlich isotherm describing Orange G adsorption over activated carbon has been illustrated in Fig. 9. The values of the Freundlich constants were calculated from the linear portions of the graph. The values of these constants are given in Table 2. The values of the exponent $1/n$ were in the range of 0 to 1, indicating favourable adsorption at all temperatures tested. The values of K_f decreased on increasing temperature thereby indicating that interaction of dye-adsorbent decreases at higher temperature.

Calculation of thermodynamic parameters :

The equilibrium constant K have been calculated from the relations¹⁸ :

$$K = C_a/C_e \quad (6)$$

where, C_e is the residual adsorbate concentration in solution at equilibrium (mg/L) and C_a is amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/L). The values of Gibbs free energy for the adsorption at different temperatures were

calculated using following expression¹⁸ :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_c \quad (7)$$

where, ΔG° is standard Gibbs free energy change, R is the universal gas constant and T is absolute temperature (K). The values of standard free energy change (ΔH°) and the standard entropy change (ΔS°) using following equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (8)$$

From eqs. (8) and (9), we obtained :

$$\ln K_c = -\Delta H^\circ/RT + \Delta S^\circ/R \quad (9)$$

The experiments were carried out at three different temperatures 303, 313 and 323 K. It was observed that the values of equilibrium constant, K_c , decreased with increase in temperature and that shows the exothermic nature of the adsorption. Hence, from the slope and intercept of plot $\ln K_c$ vs $1/T$, the value of ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained (Fig. not shown). Values of all thermodynamic parameters were given in Table 3.

Table 4. Proximate and ultimate analysis of activated carbon derived from sawdust

Proximate analysis :	
Moisture content (%)	0.19
Volatile matter (%)	64.21
Fixed carbon (%)	21.07
Ash (%)	16.53
Ultimate analysis (dry basis, wt%) :	
C (%)	53.36
H (%)	4.74
N (%)	3.2
O (%) by difference	38.7

The feasibility of the process is shown by negative values of free energy in Table 3. The decrease in value of free energy with increase in temperature suggests that the process of removal becomes more spontaneous at increasing temperatures and adsorption is favored at the lower temperature. The exothermic nature of the process is further confirmed by the negative value of enthalpy. The positive value of entropy suggests that there is increased in randomness after the adsorption of Orange G on raw saw dust.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that the removal of Orange G by adsorption on synthesized activated carbon is sig-

nificant and as the adsorbent is a 'low cost material', it can be recommended for large scale application. The removal was higher in lower range of pH. Equilibrium data fitted well in Freundlich isotherm model as compared with Langmuir's model. Thermodynamic study confirms about the spontaneity of the process and indicates that Orange G adsorption onto activated carbon is exothermic in nature. This result suggests that the synthesized activated carbon could be used as low cost material for removal of dye from aqueous solution.

Experimental

Preparation of perchloric acid treated sawdust carbon :

The saw dust was procured from the local timber factory from Allahabad. The collected materials were washed 7-8 times with distilled water to remove impurities adhere to it. The cleaned material then kept in oven for 24 h at 110 °C. The dried sawdust was mixed with concentrated perchloric acid 70% (E. Merck, India) as an activating reagent in ratio of 1 : 1.5, w/v and allowed to stand at 110 °C for 24 h in a hot air oven. The carbonized material so obtained was washed with distilled water several times to remove the free acid and soaked in 1% sodium bicarbonate solution overnight to remove any remaining acid. The material was then washed with distilled water and dried at 100 °C in a hot air oven for 24 h. It was then ground and sieved in the size range of 0.25-0.66 mm. The material so obtained was analyzed for proximate and ultimate analyses depicted in Table 4. The material obtained after activation was placed in air tight plastic containers for further use.

Adsorbate :

The dye, Orange G of chemical formula $C_{16}H_{10}N_2Na_2O_7S_2$ with FW of 452.37, selected for the present system was procured from Merck India (P.) Limited, Mumbai. The chemical structure of Orange G dye is listed in Fig. 1. Orange G (C.I. No. 16230) obtained from E. Merck (Mumbai, India) having 99.0% purity was used for the preparation dye solution without further purification. Stock solution of the test reagent was made by dissolving 1 g of dye in 1 litre of double distilled water. The stock solution was further diluted with distilled water to obtain the standard solutions of 50 mg/L, 100 mg/L and 200 mg/L.

Fig. 8. Pseudo-second order kinetic plot for the removal of Orange G (concentration 50 mg/L) at different temperatures by activated carbon.

Fig. 9. Freundlich isotherm for the removal of Orange G onto activated carbon at different temperatures.

Characterization of materials :

Infrared spectra of the adsorbents were obtained using a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (Model ABB FTLA 2000, Canada). For the FTIR study finely ground adsorbent was intimately mixed with KBr (Merck) in ratio of 1 : 100 in order to prepare translucent pellet. From the obtained spectra the presence of functional groups on the adsorbent were confirmed.

Batch mode experiments :

In the present study batch experiments were conducted in order to achieve the optimum operating conditions for the treatment process. For each experimental run 50 mL of known concentration of dye and adsorbent was taken in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The mixture was shaken mechanically at constant speed of 180 rpm using water bath shaker (Mac-Macro Scientific Works, Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India). The samples were withdrawn after predetermined time, and kept it for 24 h for saturation. Thereafter the adsorbent was separated from the solution by centrifugation using Remi centrifuge machine (Model-R-8CBL). The residual dye concentration was estimated in supernatant spectrophotometrically on double beam spectrophotometer (Model-2203 Systronics, Ahmadabad, India) over a wavelength range of 480 nm.

Adsorption kinetics investigations were carried out by agitating 50 mL of dye solution of known initial dye concentration with 10 g/L of adsorbent at temperature of 30 °C at a pH of 2.0 ± 0.1 at a constant shaking speed of 180 rpm at different interval of time. The amount of dye adsorbed onto the adsorbent at equilibrium, q_e (mg/g), can be calculated by using relationship :

$$q_e = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)V}{W} \quad (10)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium dye concentration in mg/L respectively, V is the volume of solution (L) and W is the mass of adsorbent (g). The amount of adsorption at time t , q_t (mg/g) was calculated by :

$$q_t = \frac{(C_0 - C_t)V}{W} \quad (11)$$

where C_0 and C_t in mg/g are the liquid phase concentration of dye at initial and any time t , respectively. V is the volume of solution (L) and W is the mass of dry adsor-

bent (g).

Similarly for the adsorption isotherm experiments were conducted by contacting 10 g/L of adsorbent with 50 mL of dye solution of various initial concentrations (50 mg/L, 100 mg/L, 200 mg/L). The samples were agitated in water bath at constant speed of 180 rpm at varied temperature (30 °C, 40 °C and 50 °C) for 50 min which is the equilibrium time. The residual dye concentrations were determined in the same way as mentioned above.

Blank experiments were also conducted by using dye solution without adsorbent to ensure that no dye adsorbed onto the containers and with adsorbent and water only to check that no leaching occurred, which would rather interfere with the measurement of dye concentrations on the spectrophotometer. All adsorption experiments were performed in duplicate and the mean values were use in data analysis.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the absorbance of aqueous solutions of Orange G dye was negligible between pH 2.0 and 10 so there was no marked changes in the λ_{\max} (480 nm) of dye however between pH 10 and 11.5 there was a marked decrease in absorbance, caused by dissociation of the hydroxyl on the β -naphthol ring. The present experiment was carried out over the pH range from 2 to 10 using pH meter (Model-335 Systronics, Ahmedabad, India). The pH was adjusted using 1 M HCl and NaOH solution. In this study 50 mL of dye solution of different concentration (50 mg/L, 100 mg/L and 200 mg/L) was agitated with 0.5 g of adsorbent at temperature 30 °C for 50 min. The samples were then centrifuged and filtered and the concentration in the supernatant solution determined spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 480 nm.

Determination of pH_{zpc} :

For experimental determination of pH_{zpc} of adsorbent, 0.01 M KNO_3 was adjusted in the range between 2 to 12 by using NaOH or HCl. Then 50 mL of 0.01 M KNO_3 was taken in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and 0.5 g of adsorbent was introduced in the flask at different pH. These flasks were then kept for 48 h and after that pH of the solutions were measured by using pH meter. Graphs were then plotted between pH final vs pH initial. The point of intersection of curve of pH final vs pH initial recorded as pH_{zpc} of the surface of saw dust.

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